

A Synthesis of (\pm) O-Tetramethylbrazilin

J. N. CHATTERJEA*, S. C. SHAW and N. D. SINHA

Chemical Laboratory, Patna University, Patna-5

Accepted 24 April 1974

A synthesis of racemic O-trimethylbrazilin from anhydro O-trimethylbrazilin by hydroboration is described. The derived (\pm) O-tetramethylbrazilin is shown to be different from that described in the literature.

ATTEMPTS to add elements of water to the chromene double bond of anhydro O-trimethylbrazilin (I) failed because it passed into brazylium salts most readily in the presence of acids^{1,2}. The hydroboration of (I) in ether with diborane prepared *in situ* (AlCl_3 and Na_2BH_4) or better (LiAlH_4 and BF_3) proceeded well to give *cis* O-trimethylbrazilane (IV) and when the organoborane prepared in tetrahydrofuran was oxidised by alkaline H_2O_2 , (\pm) O-Trimethylbrazilin (III) was formed. Exploratory work was carried out with success on 7-methoxy-3,4-cyclo-hexenochromene (II) (*vide* experimental). After our preliminary communication³, our notice was drawn to a similar communication (without experimental details) of Kirkiacharian and Billet⁴. The synthesis is stereo-specific and affords synthetic proof of *cis* junction in brazilin⁵.

III, R = OH
IV, R = H
V, R = oAc
VI, R = oMe

(\pm) O-Trimethylbrazilin was methylated under controlled conditions to (\pm) O-tetramethylbrazilin

* Present address: Indian Lac Research Institute, Namkum, Ranchi-10.

(VI) m.p. 116° - 17° having identical i.r. spectrum as (+) O-tetramethylbrazilin, m.p. 137° - 39° in methylene chloride solution. The compound is obviously different from Chakrabarti's product⁴, m.p. 133° - 34° . The N.M.R. spectrum of (III) showed OH proton at δ 2.74 ppm and the methylated product (VI) showed the absence of OH proton and the corresponding aliphatic $-\text{OCH}_3$ protons showed signals at δ 3.4 ppm. The N.M.R. assignments of other protons (δ) are given below:

(\pm) O-Trimethylbrazilin (III)

Aromatic Protons					
OCH_3	H at C_1	H at C_2	H at C_4	H at C_6	H at C_{11}
3.82(3),	7.31(1)	6.68(1)	6.46(1)	6.78(1)	6.72(1)
3.80(3)	J 1,2=8	J 1,2=8	J 2,4=2		
3.74(3)		2,4=2			
Aliphatic Protons					
H at C_8 (2) and C_{12} (1)		H at C_7 (2)		OH	
multiplets 4.07-3.95		$\text{C}_{7\alpha}$ 3.22 $\text{J}_{\alpha\beta} = 8$		$\text{C}_{7\beta}$ 2.83 $\text{J}_{\alpha\beta} = 8$	

(\pm) O-Tetramethylbrazilin (VI)

Aromatic Protons					
OCH_3	H at C_1	H at C_2	H at C_4	H at C_6	H at C_{11}
3.82(3),	7.31(1)	6.68(1)	6.46(1)	6.78(1)	6.72(1)
3.80(3),	J 1,2=8	J 1,2=8	J 2,4=2		
3.74(3)		2,4=2			
Aliphatic Protons					
OCH_3	H at C_8 and C_{12}		H at C_7		
3.4(3)	multiplets 4.38-4.20		$\text{C}_{7\alpha}$ 3.26 $\text{J}_{\alpha,\beta} = 8$	$\text{C}_{7\beta}$ 2.62 $\text{J}_{\alpha,\beta} = 8$	

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Unless otherwise mentioned, the i.r. spectra were determined in Perk-in-Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer, Model 237. The N.M.R. spectrum was determined in CDCl_3 at 100 Mc.

7-Methoxy 3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin :

A mixture of *m*-methoxyphenol (2.48 g) and ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (3.16 g) in dry alcohol, was saturated with hydrogen chloride at room temperature until the coumarin separated. The coumarin was filtered and crystallised from petroleum ether as fine needles (1.5 g), m.p. $105^\circ\text{--}6^\circ$ (Found : C, 72.55; H, 5.78. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 73.05; H, 5.78%); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1720 cm^{-1} . The compound on demethylation afforded the related phenol, m.p. $203^\circ\text{--}4^\circ$ (lit.⁸ m.p. $203^\circ\text{--}4^\circ$).

7-Methoxy 3,4-cyclohexenochromene (II) :

This compound was prepared by adapting the procedure of Chatterjea and co-worker⁹. 7-Methoxy-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (1.5 g) was reduced with LiAlH_4 (0.4 g, excess) in dry ether at room temperature. The mixture was left overnight and next day decomposed with dil. H_2SO_4 till there was no effervescence. The ether layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether (3×10 ml). After drying, the diol was obtained as a yellowish liquid (1 g). A solution of the diol (0.8 g) in pure diethylene glycol (35 ml) was refluxed for 25 mins. During boiling slow separation of water was noted. The mixture was cooled, diluted with water, extracted with ether and washed with NaOH solution (5%) and with water. The resulting brown liquid after removal of ether gave the *chromene* which distilled at $160^\circ\text{--}70^\circ/2$ mm as a colourless oil (Found : C, 77.98; H, 4.94. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.79; H, 5.54%); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{neat}}$ 1625 cm^{-1} (double bond).

7-Methoxy-3-hydroxy-3,4-cyclohexanochroman :

This is prepared from 7-methoxy-3,4-cyclohexenochrom-3-ene by using the experimental procedure of H. C. Brown and co-worker¹⁰.

A stirred suspension of powdered NaBH_4 (0.03 g) in dry T.H.F. (30 ml) at 0° under an atmosphere of nitrogen gas was treated with BF_3 etherate (1.5 ml) in dry T.H.F. (10 ml) over a period of 10 mins. After further 10 mins, the chromene (0.3 g) in dry T.H.F. (10 ml) was added in slow stream and the mixture was stirred for 3.5 hrs at room temperature. The reaction mixture was cooled at 0° and then treated with sodium hydroxide (30%, 30 ml) followed by hydrogen peroxide (30%, 30 ml) and stirred for another hour. The product was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was washed several times with water and dried (MgSO_4). Removal of the solvent gave a yellow liquid, distilling at $150^\circ\text{--}60^\circ/3$ mm as a colourless oil (0.15 g) (Found : C, 71.2; H, 7.05. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 71.9; H, 7.6%);

$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{neat}}$ 3350 cm^{-1} (OH).

Cis-O-Trimethylbrazilane (IV) :

To a ice-cold slurry of LiAlH_4 (0.3 g) in ether (50 ml), deoxytrimethylbrazilone (0.05 g, prepared according to literature¹) was added. BF_3 -etherate (0.3 ml in 10 ml ether) was added carefully with stirring during 2 min. The mixture was stirred for 5 hrs and decomposed carefully with dil. sulphuric acid. The ether solution on distillation gave *cis* O-trimethylbrazilane, m.p. $109^\circ\text{--}10^\circ$ identical with an authentic specimen. The compound afforded O-trimethylbrazilium ferrichloride, m.p. $20^\circ\text{--}10^\circ$ identical with an authentic specimen (m.m.p. and i.r.) on oxidation with ferric chloride in acetic acid.

(\pm) O-Trimethylbrazilin (III) :

This was prepared essentially by the same procedure as above from (I, 0.35 g). The ethereal extract after peroxide oxidation afforded an uncrystallisable residue which was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. One of the earlier fractions gave traces of a high melting product, m.p. 285° which was not examined further.

(\pm) O-Trimethylbrazilin (0.05 g) was obtained from a succeeding fraction crystallising from methanol in colourless needles, m.p. $138^\circ\text{--}39^\circ$ identical (mixed m.p. and i.r. spectrum) with a specimen supplied by Prof. Dann³. In KBr the racemic compound showed OH absorption at 3450 cm^{-1} where as the natural (+) O-trimethylbrazilin showed absorption at 3530 cm^{-1} .

(\pm) Acetyl O-Trimethylbrazilin (V) :

O-Trimethylbrazilin acetate was prepared from (\pm) O-trimethylbrazilin by refluxing with freshly distilled acetic anhydride and for 5 hrs in oil bath. It crystallised from MeOH in needles, m.p. $186^\circ\text{--}87^\circ$

(lit.³, $185^\circ\text{--}6^\circ$); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1720 and 1285 cm^{-1} ; absence of OH absorption.

(\pm) Tetramethylbrazilin (VI) :

(\pm) O-Trimethylbrazilin (50 mg) was mixed with powdered KOH, a few drops of MeOH, and excess of methyl iodide (2 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 10–12 hrs, the volatile matter removed in vacuum and diluted with water. A oily liquid separated which on rubbing gave a solid, m.p. $105^\circ\text{--}107^\circ$ which on purification by chromatography over alumina in benzene solution gave (VI) which crystallised from methyl alcohol in colourless prisms m.p. $116^\circ\text{--}17^\circ$. (+) Tetramethylbrazilin¹¹ has m.p. $137^\circ\text{--}39^\circ$. The m.p. could not be raised on further crystallisation (Found : C, 70.05; H, 6.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 70.17; H, 6.43%). The compound had superimposable i.r. spectra with (+) O-tetramethylbrazilin in methylene chloride solution (absence of OH absorption).

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to Prof. Otto Dann for providing us the (\pm) O-trimethylbrazilin. We are thankful to Sir R. Robinson for his interest in our work.

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